

Kinetics and Mechanism of the Oxidation of Phosphinic, Phenylphosphinic and Phosphorous Acids by Bis(2,2'-bipyridyl)copper(II) Permanganate

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The oxidation of three lower oxyacids of phosphorus by bis(2,2'-bipyridyl)copper(II) permanganate (BBCP) leads to the formation of the corresponding oxyacids with phosphorus in higher oxidation state. The reaction is first order with respect to both BBCP and the oxyacid. The reaction is catalysed by hydrogen ion. There is no effect of added 2,2'-bipyridine. Increase in the amount of acetic acid in the solvent mixture increases the rate. The oxidation of deuterated phosphinic and phosphorous acids exhibits substantial kinetic isotope effects. The tricoordinated form of the oxyacid is not involved in the oxidation process. Suitable mechanisms have been proposed.

Kinetic studies of the oxidation reactions of aqueous potassium permanganate, a widely used oxidising reagent, have been reported by several workers¹. But the oxidation by permanganate ions suffers from several disadvantages². To minimise these, several permanganate derivatives, incorporating different counterions, have been prepared and used as oxidising agents. The oxidising ability and selectivity of the permanganate ion seem to be dependent on the nature of the counter ion³. One such reagent is bis(2,2'-bipyridyl)copper(II) permanganate (BBPC), found to be a mild and selective oxidising agent, has been used in the oxidation of a number of organic compounds⁴. In continuation⁵ of our earlier work on the kinetics of oxidations by BBCP, we report here the kinetics of oxidation of three lower oxyacid of phosphorus, viz. phosphinic (PA), phenylphosphinic (PPA) and phosphorous (POA) acids by BBCP in aqueous acetic acid. The role of tautomeric forms of the oxyacid in the oxidation process has been examined. Mechanistic aspects are discussed.

Results and Discussion

The reactions are of first order with respect to the BBCP. Further, the values of k_{obs} are independent of the initial concentration of BBCP. The reaction rate increases linearly with an increase in the [oxyacid] (Table 1). To ascertain the importance of the cleavage of α -P-H bond in the rate-determining step, the oxidation of deuterated PA and POA was studied. The oxidation of deuterated oxyacids exhibited substantial primary kinetic isotope effects (Table 2). The reaction rate increases with an increase in the concentration of hydrogen ions (Table 3). A plot of rate vs $[H^+]$ is a curve concave to the rate axis and makes an intercept on the rate axis. The rates of oxidation of oxyacids was determined in solvents containing different proportions of acetic acid in the solvent mixture of acetic acid and water. It was observed that the rate increases with an increase in the amount of acetic acid in the solvent mixture (Table 4). Addition of 2,2'-bipyridine does not affect the rate (Table 5). This rules out the possibility of a preequilibrium involving the 2,2'-bipyridine. The oxidation of oxyacids, in an atmosphere of nitrogen, failed to induce the polymere-

TABLE 1—RATE CONSTANTS FOR OXIDATION OF THE OXYACIDS BY BBCP AT 303 K

10^3 [BBCP]	[oxyacid]	$[H^+]$	$10^4 k_{obs} (s^{-1})$		
			PA	PPA	POA
mol dm ⁻³	mol dm ⁻³	mol dm ⁻³			
1.0	0.12	1.0	3.67	6.90	1.44
1.0	0.24	1.0	7.26	13.6	3.00
1.0	0.48	1.0	14.6	27.8	5.73
1.0	0.72	1.0	22.0	41.2	8.64
1.0	0.96	1.0	29.5	54.3	11.7
1.0	1.20	1.0	36.0	69.9	14.6
2.0	0.48	1.0	15.0	27.6	5.33
4.0	0.48	1.0	14.2	28.2	5.75
8.0	0.48	1.0	14.9	28.0	5.86
1.0	0.48	1.0 ^a	14.3	28.1	5.61

^a Contained 0.001 mol dm⁻³ acrylonitrile.

TABLE 2—KINETIC ISOTOPE EFFECT ON THE OXIDATION OF PHOSPHINIC AND PHOSPHOROUS ACIDS

Temp. = 303 K and $[H^+] = 0.1 \text{ mol dm}^{-3}$

Acid	$10^4 k_2 (\text{dm}^3 \text{ mol}^{-1} \text{ s}^{-1})$		k_H / k_D
	H	D	
PA	57.2	11.8	4.85
POA	12.0	2.66	4.51

TABLE 3—DEPENDENCE OF REACTION RATE ON HYDROGEN ION CONCENTRATION

[PA] = 0.24 mol dm⁻³, [BBCP] = 0.0005 mol dm⁻³, temp. = 303 K

$[H^+]$	0.1	0.2	0.4	0.6	0.8	1.0	1.2	1.5	2.0
(mol dm ⁻³)									
$10^4 k_{obs} (s^{-1})$	7.26	9.11	13.1	16.81	20.5	35.7	49.0	72.7	125

TABLE 4—EFFECT OF SOLVENT COMPOSITION ON THE OXIDATION OF PHOSPHINIC ACID

[PA] = 0.12 mol dm⁻³, [BBCP] = 0.0005 mol dm⁻³, $[H^+] = 0.1 \text{ mol dm}^{-3}$, temp. = 303K

AcOH (% v/v)	20	40	50	60	70	80
$10^4 k_{obs} (s^{-1})$	1.10	2.85	3.67	7.10	16.7	30.3

TABLE 5—EFFECT OF 2,2'-BIPYRIDINE ON THE OXIDATION OF 2-PROPANOL BY BBCP

[PA] = 0.24 mol dm⁻³, [BBCP] = 0.0005 mol dm⁻³, $[H^+] = 0.1 \text{ mol dm}^{-3}$, temp. = 298 K

[bpy] (mol dm ⁻³)	0.00	0.01	0.02	0.03	0.05
$10^4 k_{obs} (s^{-1})$	7.26	7.35	7.40	7.12	7.10

risation of acrylonitrile. Further, the addition of acrylonitrile had no effect on the reaction rate (Table 1). Thus a one-electron oxidation, giving rise free radicals, is unlikely. The rate of oxidation of the three oxyacids were determined at different temperatures and the activation parameters were calculated (Table 6).

TABLE 6—TEMPERATURE DEPENDENCE AND THE ACTIVATION PARAMETERS OF THE OXIDATION OF OXYACIDS OF PHOSPHORUS BY BBP

Acid	$k_2 / \text{dm}^3 \text{ mol}^{-1} \text{ s}^{-1}$				ΔH^* kJ mol ⁻¹	ΔS^* J mol ⁻¹ K ⁻¹	ΔG^* kJ mol ⁻¹
	293K	303K	313K	323K			
PA	3.04	5.72	10.3	19.1	45.5±0.6	-139±2	86.6±0.5
PPA	9.00	15.1	26.0	43.8	39.1±0.6	-151±2	84.0±0.5
POA	0.52	1.20	2.17	4.30	5.20±1.3	-130±3	906±1.1

An analysis of the data on hydrogen ion dependence revealed that at moderate concentrations of hydrogen ions ($[\text{H}^+] \leq 0.8 \text{ mol dm}^{-3}$), it has the form, $k_{\text{obs}} = a + b[\text{H}^+]$ ($a = 5.38 \pm 0.01 \times 10^{-4} \text{ s}^{-1}$; $b = 1.90 \pm 0.02 \times 10^{-3} \text{ mol}^{-1} \text{ dm}^3 \text{ s}^{-1}$; $r^2 = 0.9998$) and at higher concentrations of hydrogen ions, ($[\text{H}^+] \geq 1.0 \text{ mol dm}^{-3}$), it has the form, $k_{\text{obs}} = a + c[\text{H}^+]^2$ ($a = 6.00 \pm 0.22 \times 10^{-4} \text{ s}^{-1}$; $c = 2.97 \pm 0.01 \times 10^{-3} \text{ mol}^{-2} \text{ dm}^6 \text{ s}^{-1}$; $r^2 = 0.9996$). This observation led us to propose that the reaction follows an acid-independent path and two acid-dependent paths involving singly protonated and doubly protonated forms of a reactant at moderate and higher concentrations of hydrogen ion respectively.

The increase in the value of k_{obs} with an increase in the amount of acetic acid in the solvent mixture can be explained on the basis of change in the acidity of the medium with a change in the amount of acetic acid. Wiberg and Evans⁶ determined the Hammett's acidity function (H_0) for low concentrations of perchloric acid in a series of acetic acid-water mixtures. They observed that the acidity increases as the water concentration decreases. The reaction under investigation is acid-catalysed one and with an increase in the acidity of the solution, the rate is expected to increase.

Reactive reducing species : Lower oxyacids of phosphorus are reported⁷ to exist in two tautomeric forms (eqn. 1). The tricoordinated tautomer (B) is thought to be produced as an intermediate in the exchange of phosphorus-bonded hydrogen with deuterium and tritium. The value⁸ of the equilibrium constant (K_t) is of the order of 10^{-12} .

Hence two alternative mechanisms can be postulated. As-

suming only the pentacoordinated tautomer (A) as the reactive form, the following mechanism may be proposed, leading to the rate law (3)

$$\text{Rate} = k_a [\text{oxyacid}]_0 [\text{BBP}] / (1 + K_t [\text{oxyacid}]_0) \quad (3)$$

where, $[\text{oxyacid}]_0$ represents the initial concentration of the oxyacid. Eqn. (3) is reduced to eqn. (4) as $1 \gg K_t$,

$$\text{Rate} = k_a [\text{oxyacid}]_0 [\text{BBP}] \quad (4)$$

Another mechanism can be written assuming the tricoordinate form (B) as the reactive reducing species,

This mechanism leads to the rate law (6), which can be reduced to (7) again acknowledging that $1 \gg K_t$,

$$\text{Rate} = K_t k_b [\text{oxyacid}]_0 [\text{BBP}] / (1 + K_t [\text{oxyacid}]_0) \quad (6)$$

$$\text{Rate} = K_t k_b [\text{oxyacid}]_0 [\text{BBP}] \quad (7)$$

Thus the two rate equations conform to the experimental rate law and are kinetically indistinguishable.

If equations (1) and (5) represent the mechanism of the oxidation of oxyacids of phosphorus then the experimental specific rate constant, $k_2 = K_t k_b$. The value of K_t is of the order of 10^{-12} . Therefore, the value of rate-limiting constant (k_b) ranges between 10^8 and $10^{10} \text{ dm}^3 \text{ mol}^{-1} \text{ s}^{-1}$. This value exceeds/equals the rate constants of diffusion-controlled rate processes⁹. Therefore, the participation of the tricoordinated form of the oxyacids in the oxidation process can be ruled out.

Mechanism : Not much is known about the structure of BBP. In particular, the nature of bonding of the permanganate anions with the $[\text{bpy}_2\text{Cu}(\text{II})]$ cation is not certain. However, in the corresponding halide complexes, it has been shown that one halide ion is joined to the central metal atom by a covalent bond and another by an electrovalent bond¹⁰. Based on that analogy, BBP may also be represented as $[\text{bpy}_2\text{Cu}(\text{MnO}_4)]\text{MnO}_4$.

The presence of a substantial primary kinetic isotope effect confirms the cleavage of a P-H bond in the rate-determining step. A preferential cleavage of P-H bond, in the rate-determining step, is likely in view of the relatively high bond dissociation energy of the O-H bond. The mean value¹¹ of the bond dissociation energy of a O-H bond is

460 kJ mol⁻¹ while that for a P-H bond¹² is 321 kJ mol⁻¹. A one-electron oxidation, giving rise to free radicals, is unlikely in view of the absence of any effect of acrylonitrile on the reaction. There is no kinetic evidence of the formation of an intermidate/adduct, though its formation in very small amounts can not be ruled out. In many previous studies involving BBCP⁵, the formation of an ester/anhydride intermediate has been suggested. Therefore, it is proposed that this reaction also involves formation of an anhydride in a pre-equilibrium but the value of equilibrium constant is very small. The following mechanism accounts for all the experimental results (Scheme 1). Alternatively, the hydride ion transfer may take place directly leading to

Acid-independent path :

Acid-dependent path :

Scheme 1

Acid-independent path :

Acid-dependent path :

Scheme 2

the formation of a phosphinium cation intermidate (Scheme 2). In this case the hydrogen-ion catalysis may well be due to be protolysis of BBCP to yield permanganic acid and its protonated form.

Experimental

The phosphorus oxyacids (commercial products, Fluka) were used as supplied. Their aqueous solutions were standardised by alkalimetry. BBCP was prepared by the reported method¹³ and its purity was checked by an iodometric method. The P-H bonds in PA and POA were deuteriated by repeatedly dissolving the acid in deuterium oxide (BARC, 99.4%) and evaporating water and the excess of deuterium oxide under reduced pressure¹⁴. The isotopic purity of the deuteriated PA and POA, as determined from their nmr spectra, was 91 ± 4% and 93 ± 5% respectively. Acetic acid was refluxed with CrO₃ and acetic anhydride for 6 h and then distilled. Perchloric acid (Merck) was used as a source of hydrogen ions.

Stoichiometry : The oxidation of lower oxyacids of phosphorus leads to the formation of corresponding oxyacids containing phosphorus in a higher oxidation state.

Reaction mixtures were prepared containing a known excess of phosphinic or phosphorus acid. On the completion of reaction, amount of phosphorus acid formed in the oxidation of phosphinic acid and the residual reductant in the oxidation of phosphorus acid were determined by the reported method¹⁵. To determine the stoichiometry of the oxidation of PPA, a known excess of BBCP was treated with PPA and the residual BBCP was determined spectrophotometrically at 529 nm after the completion of the reaction. Iodometric determination of a completely reduced reaction mixture, showed that the oxidation state of the reduced manganese is 3.89 ± 0.20. The overall reaction may written as

To confirm the formation of Mn⁴⁺ as results of the reduction of BBCP by the oxyacid, rates were determined by monitoring the increase in [Mn^{IV}] at 418 nm also¹⁶. The results showed that the rates of decay at 529 nm and of increase at 418 nm agreed within ± 10%. BBCP had virtually no absorption at 418 nm. This agrees with the observations of earlier workers¹⁶.

Kinetic measurements : The reactions were carried out under pseudo-first order conditions by maintaining a large excess of the oxyacid (× 15 or more) over BBCP. The solvent was 1 : 1 (v/v) acetic acid-water mixture, unless mentioned otherwise. The reactions were carried out at a constant temperature (± 0.1 K) and followed up to 80% reaction by monitoring the decrease in [BBCP] at 529 nm. The pseudo-first order rate constants (*k*_{obs}) were computed from

the linear ($r > 0.990$) least-squares plots of $\log [\text{BBCP}]$ vs time. Duplicate kinetic runs showed that the rate constants were reproducible within $\pm 3\%$. The second order rate constant (k_2) was obtained by the relation, $k_2 = k_{\text{obs}} [\text{oxyacid}]$

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